

SEMANTICS AND PRAGMATICS OF THE SPEECH VERBS IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the study of semantics and pragmatics of the speech verbs in the English language. In this the article the factors and conditions that determine the process of functional categorization of the linguistic picture of the world, as well as to determine the specifics of the functional categorization of three groups of verbs, respectively, with the prototypes tell, say and speak is identified.

Keywords: semantics, pragmatics, speech verbs, factors, conditions, specific, categorization, tell, say, speak.

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Introduction. Speech verbs have repeatedly been the object of linguistic research, which studied their lexical and categorical semantics, as well as their functioning in various structures. In the linguistic literature, the nomenclature of the semantic structure of the group of verbs under consideration is described quite fully at the system-paradigmatic level, there is also data concerning the features of their functioning in the sentence - utterance. However, there are still no works in linguistics that consider the functional categorization of speech verbs with a description of the mechanism of variation of their categorical status from the standpoint of functional - semiological and prototypical approaches to the formation of the categorical meaning of predicative units.

Speech verbs are one of the most researched objects in linguistic research. The interest in this group of lexical units is due to both the complexity of their semantic structure and the ambiguity in the issue of identifying synonymous series and thematic groups.

The relevance of the research is due to the need for a general theoretical understanding of the processes of functional categorization of speech verbs, clarifying the mechanism that determines the features of functional categorization at the formal (syntactic), semantic and conceptual levels, and the conditions for the formation of a special lexical and categorical meaning of these verbs within the sentence - utterance.

The relevance of the research is also determined by the goals and objectives of teaching active and correct command of a foreign language.

The purpose of the article is to identify the factors and conditions that determine the process of functional categorization of the linguistic picture of the world, as well as to determine the specifics of the functional categorization of three groups of verbs, respectively, with the prototypes *tell*, *say* and *speak*.

The goal dictates the following research objectives:

1. Definition and description of mechanisms and conditions of functional categorization of speech verbs.
2. Identification of criteria and conditions under which a syncretic change in the categorical and lexical meaning of the verbs under study is possible.
3. Comparison of the system-paradigmatic and functional levels of the analysis of speech verbs.
4. Clarification of the nomenclature of prototypical action and non-action characteristics of speech verbs.
5. Establishing the degree of dependence of the categorical status of the predicate on its subject-object relations in the sentence-utterance structural scheme.
6. Determination of the set of the most recurrent lexical units capable of transmitting the meanings of unidirectional/unidirectional speaking.

Semantic analysis of speech verbs. Speech verbs and various approaches to their study in modern English. In linguistics, the study of speech verbs (communicative verbs) went in different directions both local and foreign scientists set themselves different tasks. This class of verbs was studied from the point of view of their lexical and grammatical semantics, from the point of view of the syntactic properties of these verbs, at the functional level, in the aspect of the relationship between thinking and speech, from the point of view of the logical and semantic properties of the verbs of speech.

For a long time, the object of analysis were verbs that denote only the process of speech in its pure form. Verbs, however, realizing some activity in the act of speech, were excluded from the circle of those considered. In the light of this approach, it is believed that verbs of speech denote an action (in a broad sense) performed by the speech apparatus, that is, the pronunciation of articulate sounds (individual words or phrases) in the process of speech communication. For a long time, two main groups were distinguished in the thematic group of verbs containing an indication of the speech process:

a) verbs denoting the actual process of speech and its main functions (message, conversation, story): *tell*, *say*, *speak*, *talk*.

b) verbs denoting some other action that can be implemented in the process of speech: *command*, *order*, *affirm*, *repeat*.

In turn, verbs denoting the actual process of speech can be divided into two subgroups:

1. Verbs, in the semantics of which there is a designation of one of the functions of the speech process in its pure form, without additional characteristics:

a) verbs of the most general designation of the speech process: tell, say, speak, talk.

b) verbs of a narrower designation of the speech process: narrate, express, repeat, declare.

2. Verbs containing additional characteristics of the speech process – its duration, beginning, end, sound power, clarity of pronunciation, and so on. As a rule, verbs with additional adverbial words that characterize this process are highlighted here.

The founders of this approach to the study of verbs of speech were inclined to believe that these linguistic units call the process of speech in its most general content. In other words, the verbs under study should be considered outside of the additional characteristics of sound, tone, and emotional evaluation. We can disclose any additional information about the utterance only if the verb has one of the constructions showing the content of the utterance or the subject of speech: constructions with direct or indirect complement, with direct speech or with additional adjuncts or circumstances.

In further studies, the relationship between the lexical-grammatical compatibility of the verb and its lexical meaning began to be taken into account:

1. identifying with which parts of speech, in which forms or with which syntactic constructions the speech verbs are combined

2. determining the nature of the relationship between the meaning of the verb and its compatibility.

The founders of this approach refer to the thematic category of speech verbs those verbs that, as dictionary units, denote the process of speaking out of context. Along with the general semantic feature of the whole group expression of the speech process, each verb also indicates a certain speech act. Some speech verbs express the actual processes of communication, others denote the processes of speech associated with other aspects of human life and activity – the expression of will, the manifestation of various emotions.

Thus, verbs in the semantics of which speech is combined with evaluation, causation, truth, and so on, also fell into the spectrum of analyzed verbs. In this regard, the proponents of this approach distinguish three large groups:

a) verbs denoting the actual process of speaking;

b) verbs denoting the process of speech and characterizing it depending on the tasks of communication;

c) verbs denoting the processes of speech associated with other aspects of human life and activity.

The verbs of the first group do not express the content of the utterance and do not reflect the connection with other aspects of human life. It only indicates the very act of pronunciation (words, phrases) in the process of speech communication.

In the verbs of the second group, not only the action of speaking is expressed, but also its character is determined – the content or theme of the utterance. Here, in the verb itself, there is an indication of some other process that characterizes speaking in relation to content. The third group includes verbs that denote an action that has an external manifestation through the process of speech, that is, the expression of an act of will in words.

It is important that the features of lexical and grammatical compatibility of verbs can be indicated by syntactic constructions that are not due to the laws of the construction of phrases, but the structure of the whole sentence as a whole, for example, some combinations of a verb with an infinitive, as well as combinations of a verb with direct speech and subordinate clauses.

The syntactic connection of verbs with various adverbial determinants of the mode of action, which betray energy, attentiveness, intensity, thoroughness (carefully, immediately, perfectly, strongly, easily, precisely etc.) indicates the active, agentive nature of the subject. The forms of progressive, imperative, compatibility with modal and phase verbs, as well as with actionable verbs as homogeneous members act as additional actualizes of the subject's activity sign [3, 14].

The advantage of this approach is that a detailed examination of the compatibility of each verb helps to identify the connections of speech verbs with various forms of other words or whole constructions in the sentence and determine the dependence of these connections on the lexical meaning of the verb.

In further studies of this lexico-semantic group of verbs, scientists focused on all verbs that normatively perform the function of speech production, which significantly expanded the boundaries of this class.

Proponents of this theory took as a basis a three-level idea of the speech act, first proposed by J. Austin, in which three aspects are distinguished: locative, illocutive and perlocutive.

It should be noted that for J. Searle [3, 59-82], the successor of the ideas of J.L. Austin [1, 33] theory of speech acts was primarily a theory of meaning. J. Searle [3, 62] focused on one of the three levels of the speech act – illocutionary. An illocutionary act is an action that we perform by uttering a certain phrase (we can convince someone, ask, accuse, instruct), it should be distinguished from a locative act – by itself pronouncing some sounds or writing some signs on paper – and a perlocutionary act – the effect of our utterance on actions, thoughts or the emotions of the listeners (our statement may or may not convince the interlocutor, etc.). J.

Searle believed that the main purpose of language is not to describe the objects of reality, but to carry out purposeful actions; therefore, in search of an answer to the question: "What is the meaning?", he moved from the level of a single word to the level of a unit of communication, with the help of which a separate action is carried out, that is, to the level of an illocutionary act.

J. Searle [3, 265-277], in turn, was inclined to believe that the study of speech acts is of great interest and is important for the philosophy of language. An essential feature of any kind of language communication is that it includes a language act. Contrary to popular belief, the basic unit of linguistic communication is not a symbol, not a word, not a sentence, or even a specific instance of a symbol, word or sentence, but the production of this particular instance during the performance of a speech act. More precisely, the production of a specific sentence under certain conditions is an illocutionary act, and an illocutionary act is the minimum unit of linguistic communication.

In a typical speech situation involving the speaker, the listener, and the speaker's utterance, a wide variety of types of acts are associated with the utterance. When speaking, the speaker sets the speech apparatus in motion, pronounces sounds. At the same time, he performs other acts: informs listeners, or causes them irritation or boredom. He also carries out acts consisting in mentioning certain persons, places.

In addition, the speaker makes a statement or asks a question, gives a command or reports, congratulates or warns, that is, commits an act from among those that Austin called illocutionary.

Examples of English verbs associated with illocutionary acts are: *state* "to state", *assert* "to assert, to declare", *describe* "to describe", *warn* "to warn", *remark* "to notice", *comment* "to comment", "to command", *order* "to order", *request* "to ask", *approve* "to approve".

It should be noted that the true discovery, the honor of which belongs to J. L. Austin [1, 33], there was the allocation of a special class of performative verbs, the use of which in the first person of the present tense of the indicative mood means not just speaking, but a certain action: I promise... and, therefore, from this moment I bind myself with a promise.

Let's take a closer look at the class of verbs called performatives. As is known, actual speech is based on a number of relatively independently functioning types of communicative activity, represented by locative, illocutive and perlocutive acts and described by the corresponding types of verbs. These speech acts can be divided into actions that actualize the plan of expression of an integral communicative act and its content plan. The first are locative acts, the second are illocutive-perlocutive.

Modern researchers developing the theory of speech activity consider not only speech impact, but also communicative interaction in general. G.G. Pocheptsov, exploring illocutionary units, identifies two semes that are mandatory for these verbs:

1) an illocutionary sema characterizing the pragmatic type of the illocutionary act being denoted and 2) a locative sema (the sema of speaking).

Thus, he believes that not all speech verbs are illocutive. For example, in the meaning of the verbs voice, whisper, there is a locative sema, but there is no illocutionary one. On the other hand, some verbs can be interpreted as both locative and perlocative. For example, add, go on are among the locative ones. It is interesting to note that the verb say in its classification combines both a locative and an illocutive meaning (state, promise).

According to Z.Wendler [2,163], who provides grammatical criteria for recognizing illocutionary verbs, the class of speech verbs can be attributed to the number of performatives. Semantic unity of the class of performatives Z. Wendler demonstrates with the help of formulas used by J. Austin, introducing the concept of a performative. As it turns out, a lot of verbs that can be used as part of these formulas, and a lot of verbs that meet syntactic criteria, more or less coincide. In addition, the variety of performatives reflects the difference in the ways in which something can be said, which reveals the fact that the verb say "to speak/say", in its basic sense, is the most common performative. This formulation confirms the position of E. V. Paducheva [4, 12] says that each illocutionary act corresponds to a certain performative verb. A speech act belongs to one or another type in accordance with its illocutionary function.

Recently, a qualitatively new approach to the analysis of linguistic phenomena has appeared – cognitive. The object of cognitive linguistics research is the nature and essence of knowledge and cognition, the results of perception of reality and cognitive activity of a person accumulated in the form of meaningful and brought into a certain system of information. The study of the problem of conceptualization in the language of the surrounding reality is extremely relevant. Within the framework of cognitive linguistics, it is supposed to study various structures of knowledge underlying linguistic functioning. In this regard, the primary task is to identify concepts, analyze their structure and content.

In line with the latest research on cognitive linguistics, scientists are attracted by the idea of a comprehensive description, systematization and hierarchy of concepts as forms of representation and storage of human knowledge about the world. Nevertheless, of particular interest are, first of all, specific mechanisms and forms of realization of this knowledge by means of language, since the analysis of concepts as cognitive phenomena in which our knowledge of the surrounding

world and the principles of utterance formation are fixed is possible if they find their expression through linguistic means.

In relation to the semantic analysis of linguistic units, the essence of the cognitive approach is to explain how and to what extent cognitive information is reflected in the semantics of the word, that is, the whole complex of knowledge about the world acquired by a person in the course of his subject-cognitive and creative activity. Cognitive analysis considers not only the established facts of social knowledge fixed by social practice, but also takes into account the individual characteristics of the speaker's linguistic practice, phenomena of a temporary, situational nature.

From the point of view of the formation of the utterance, the verb is of particular interest for research, since the verb is a unit in the semantics of which the phenomena of the surrounding world are conceptualized by presenting the situation of objective reality as an action, process or state. After all, it is the verb, to a greater extent than other parts of speech, that has the ability to nominate complex structures of knowledge with a variety of cognitive characteristics in a collapsed, compressing form.

In other words, a specific phenomenon of the surrounding reality is nominated by a verb as a lexical unit with an individualized content that can carry new information.

REFERENCES:

1. John Langshaw Austin: *How to Do Things With Words*. Cambridge (Mass.) 1962, paperback: Harvard University Press, 2nd edition, 2005, ISBN 0-674-41152-8. – P.33.

2. Вендлер З. Иллокутивное самоубийство // Новое в зарубежной лингвистике. Вып. 16. – М., 1985. – С.163.

3. John Searle, *Speech Acts*, Cambridge University Press 1969, ISBN 0-521-09626-X; John Searle, "Indirect speech acts." In *Syntax and Semantics, 3: Speech Acts*, ed. P. Cole & J. L. Morgan, pp. 59–82. New York: Academic Press. (1975). Reprinted in *Pragmatics: A Reader*, ed. S. Davis, pp. 265–277. Oxford: Oxford University Press. (1991)

4. Падучева Е.В. Вид и время перформативного глагола. // Логический анализ языка: Язык речевых действий. – М., 1994. – С.12.

5. Дворник О.Д. Функциональная категоризация глаголов говорения в современном английском языке. Автореф. дисс. ... докт. филол. наук. Белгород, 2003. Серль Дж. Что такое речевой акт? // Зарубежная лингвистика. II. – М., 1999. – С.14.

6.Gadoeva M.I. Features of connotative meaning of somatisms as part of phraseological units // *International Journal on Integrated Education*. Volume 3, Issue III, March, 2020. – P.73-78. (Impact Factor: SJIF 2020 – 5,712)

7.Gadoeva M.I. Lexico-semantic fields of “eye” in English and Uzbek languages // *Academicia. An International multidisciplinary Research Journal*. ISSN (online): 2249-7137. Vol. 11, Issue 10, October. <https://saarj.com> DOI NUMBER 10.5958/2249-7137.2021.02176.5. -India, 2021. – P.872-879. (Impact Factor: SJIF 2021 - 7.492)

8.Gadoeva M.I. Semantics of somatism in blessings of English and Uzbek cultures // *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal Open Access, Peer reviewed Journal*. ISSN: 2776-0979. Volume 2, Issue 11, November, 2021. – P. 269-276. (Impact Factor: SJIF 2021 – 5,599). *Fars Int J Edu Soc Sci Hum* 10(12); 2022; **Publishing centre of Finland** 382

9.Gadoeva M.I. Expression of the somatisms "mouth", "ear", "nose", "tongue" in the system of different languages // *Novateur Publications JournalNX – A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal*. ISSN No: 2581 – 4230. Volume 7, Issue 11, Nov. -2021. –P.125-130. (JIF -7.223).

10.Gadoeva M.I. Lexico-semantic Classification of Somatisms in Phraseological Funds of English and Uzbek Languages // *Eurasian Research Bulletin. Open Access, peer research journal*. –Belgium, 2022. –V.4. –P.140-145. www.geniusjournals.org. (JIF – 7.995).

11.Gadoeva M.I. Significant features of somatic vocabulary // *Namangan davlat universiteti axborotnomasi*. – Namangan, 2021. –№12. –B. 411-416. (10.00.00; №26)

12.Gadoeva M.I. Expression of somatisms in curses // *Eurasians journal of research, development and innovation*. Genius journals publishing group. Belgium, 2021. – P.30-33.

13.Gadoeva M.I. The Expression of Somatisms in English and Uzbek Proverbs // *European Conference on Natural Research*. <http://papers.onlineconferences.com/index.php/titfl/issue/view/Stockholm>. –Sweden, 2021. – P. 36- 41.

14.Gadoeva M.I. Polysemy of Somatisms in English and Uzbek Languages // *International Conference on Multidisciplinary Research and Innovative Technology's*. November 11th, <https://academiascience.org/>. –India. 2021, – P. 87- 90.

15.Gadoeva M.I. Background analysis of somatic phraseological units in Uzbek // *Proceeding of International Conference on Research Innovation In Multidisciplinary Sciences, Hosted From New York*. www.econferenceglobe.com. – USA. 2021. –P. 297-300.

16. Gadoeva M.I. Interpretation of “head-bosh”, “foot-oyoq” and “heart-yurak (qalb)” in English and Uzbek languages // Models and methods for increasing the efficiency of innovative research: a collection scientific works of the International scientific conference (11 November) ISSUE 5. – Copenhagen. 2021. – P.61-65.

17. R.R.Kasimova. The Distinctive Writing Style of Arthur Conan Doyle // International Journal on Integrated Education. Volume 5, Issue 4, Apr 2022. - P. 197-201.

18. R.R.Kasimova. Comparative study of a Writer’s and Translator’s Psychology in the English translation of “Kecha va Kunduz” // VI. Uluslararası Türklerin Dünyası Sosyal Bilimler Sempozyum. Moldova, 13-15 may, 2022.

19. Ziyaeva D. Different meaning of the speech verbs say, tell, speak, talk. International Journal of on Integrated Education. Vol.3. Issue1. January 2020. ISSN 2620-3502. – P.95-97.

20. Ziyaeva D. Verbs of speech activity in the newspapers. International scientific journal ISJ. Theoretical and Applied science Phylodelfia. USA Issue 04. Vol.84. April 30. 2020. Journal available by link: <http://t-science.org/arxivDOI/2020/04-84.html>. Registered in Publishers International Linking Association (Lynnfield, MA, USA) Chief editor of the ISJ «Theoretical & Applied Science» импакт-фактор: 8.997 – P.1005-1008.